

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN MODERN SOCIETY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7494021>

Abstract: The article examines the problem of developing the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, special attention was paid to the organizational structure of the higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, priority directions aimed at improving the quality of scientific and professional education. In this regard, we considered it a special aspect of our article to pay attention to the following in the process of personnel training: obtaining quality indicators that meet international standards and transnationalization; ensuring the quality of higher education. The main trends of the experience of European countries regarding the mechanism of stimulating the activities of higher educational institutions and the formation of the educational system in Uzbekistan were considered.

Key words: higher education, higher education institutions, development trends, academic freedom, independent education, cyber security, digital economy, "University Company".

It creates the necessary conditions for the residents of our country to live a decent life, to get an education at the level of world standards and to acquire a profession, to take a decent civil position in the society and to realize their creative potential. The basic meaning of this lies in creating a healthy generation and raising them appropriately. Here we are We can say that the end of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century is characterized by the emergence of new approaches to the development of the higher education system.

To date, a number of trends in the development of higher education and professional training are emerging. In particular, in order to strengthen the activities of educational institutions at the international level: to develop the basis of social integration of knowledge and information provided by them and their interaction; recognition by civil society of international organizations, governments and representatives of the business community as the basis of competitiveness in the international labor market; implementation of social and economic goals; formation of partnership relations; It is planned to attract large-scale investments in the development of higher education to ensure the effective training of future specialists.

Here we should mention that higher education is one of the priorities of social policy in every country. It is the quality and convenience of higher education that reflect the country's development prospects and create a basis for training highly qualified personnel. It is in our country that various reforms are implemented every year in connection with the development of this sector. In particular, in order to fundamentally improve the system of higher education and science, to increase the quality of personnel training, the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was developed. , on the basis of ensuring a strong integration of science, education and production, the important tasks of improving the quality of education, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, and the development of international cooperation have been determined.

As a result of the reforms in the higher education system, in 2015 the number of higher education institutions in the Republic was 72, and due to the reforms of recent years, there are a total of 159 higher education institutions in the Republic, including 28 universities, 47 institutes, 3 academies, and 26 branches. , we can point out that there are 1 Conservatory, 30 branches of Foreign Higher Education Institutions.

Also, in the fourth priority of the President's decree "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", it is determined to increase the level of coverage with higher education to 50% and increase the quality of education, which is aimed at training highly qualified personnel and developing higher education in the country. it should be noted that it is an important stage.

In general, although there are achievements in the field of higher education, there are a number of problems in the higher education system. Especially in today's information age, you can almost regularly find news or materials about higher education issues on social networks. Among them, there are problems related to transition to distance education, changes in higher education legislation. We have set ourselves the goal of reforming the existing problems in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and making suggestions and recommendations regarding them.

In conclusion, knowledge is power these days. The more knowledge a person has, the more power he has. The document provided a framework that reflected the importance of holistic education in higher education for workforce placement. The article also focuses on effectiveness and participation, teaching facilitators' pedagogies, evaluation and feedback to justify the term demographic dividend. It is time to inculcate reforms and make fundamental changes,

otherwise our youth risk becoming a demographic liability. Also, one of the problems is the organization of the educational process on the basis of outdated educational programs that do not meet the requirements of the times. The complexity of the texts in the educational literature and the fact that the teaching is conducted mainly theoretically are aimed at strengthening the students' independent learning, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, entrepreneurial skills, organizational skills and competencies in the educational process. does not allow the formation of methods and technologies, limits the creative approach of teachers. Sometimes, there is a lack of systematicity, and therefore the knowledge acquired at the initial stage is not supplemented at higher stages.

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